

Effect of Separator Vacuum Valve on the Quality of Cotton Raw Materials

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Abstract: This article theoretically analyzes the importance of ensuring the quality of raw materials and increasing their high efficiency in the cotton production process. One of the factors affecting the quality of cotton is, of course, the quality of equipment and processes. In particular, the role of the separator vacuum valve in the operation process is one of the main factors determining the quality of cotton raw materials. However, tribological phenomena, namely friction, wear and lubrication problems, may occur during the operation of the separator. These tribological phenomena can degrade the quality of cotton raw materials and reduce the efficiency of the production process. Therefore, methods for analyzing these phenomena and eliminating them are important in maintaining cotton quality.

Keywords: tribology, lubrication, friction, wear, fiber, vacuum valve, innovative technology, monitoring systems, and optimization.

Introduction. In cotton production, separators are one of the main equipments, which are used for separating and cleaning cotton from the air flow. Vacuum valves play an important role in the operation of separators. The vacuum valve ensures the efficient operation of the separator and transfers the cotton raw material that is collected. Tribology is a scientific field that studies the processes of friction, wear and lubrication, and its importance in the cotton industry is very great. The following tribological phenomena can occur in mechanical systems such as separator vacuum valves:

Friction: Friction that occurs between components during operation in separator vacuum valves reduces the efficiency of the system and leads to energy loss. Friction can damage cotton fibers, reducing their purity and quality.

Wear: Wear caused by friction in separator vacuum valves reduces the durability of components and shortens their service life. Cotton fibers can be damaged because wear increases the interaction between the valves and the cotton. **Lubrication System Issues:** Separator vacuum valves require a lubrication system to operate effectively. Insufficient lubrication or an improper lubrication system can negatively affect the quality of the cotton raw material. Excessive oil or improper lubrication, which can damage the cotton, reduces operating efficiency. When the cotton raw material is fed to the separator, the vacuum system removes excess air and dust, which helps maintain the unique structure and quality of the cotton.

Scientific research methods. Tribological phenomena can affect the performance of separator vacuum valves and lead to the following negative consequences:

- **Effect on cotton cleanliness:** Friction and abrasion damage cotton fibers. Improper operation of the system can disrupt the cleaning process of cotton and cause deformation and excessive pressure.
- **Cotton fiber breakage:** Friction and abrasion can cause cotton fibers to easily bunch and harden. This

negatively affects the quality of the cotton and makes its processing difficult.

- Other harmful facts: Tribological phenomena in the separator vacuum valves can disrupt the efficient operation of the system, reducing the overall efficiency of the cotton production process. Excessive heating or increased resistance in the system can occur, which negatively affects the quality of the cotton fibers.

There are several factors that affect the cotton flow on the separator and vacuum valve surfaces. The speed at which the flow hits the surface determines the force exerted on the separator surface and the direction in which the flow is directed. High-speed flow can increase the force exerted on the surface. If the flow is at an angle or slant to the surface, the distribution of the force exerted on the separator surface changes, which can affect the separation efficiency. The physical properties of the flow, i.e. its viscosity and density, determine how it affects the separator surface. Solids or air will have a greater impact on the surface and may be more effective in the separation process. The shear forces (forces parallel to the surface) that arise as a result of the flow acting on the surface help to separate the liquid or create a larger separation surface. Depending on the type of flow, the forces acting on the separator surface and the characteristics of the flow change. Turbulent flow tends to favor sedimentation or separation processes, while laminar flow tends to favor a more controlled and simpler process.

FIGURE 2. EFFECT OF COTTON FLOW ON SEPARATOR SURFACE

1-input tube , 2-cotton mass flow , 3-body, 4-acting surface ,
5-working chamber , 6-vacuum valve

Vacuum valves have a significant impact on the efficient operation of separators. If the vacuum system is not properly adjusted or does not work, it can negatively affect the quality of the cotton. For example, a malfunctioning vacuum valve can lead to incomplete separation of the cotton and contamination with foreign substances. Therefore, optimal operation of the separator vacuum valve is essential to ensure the quality of the cotton.

FIGURE 3. DESTRUCTION OF SEPARATOR WALLING UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF COTTON FLOW

Results. Tribological phenomena can be eliminated through a number of measures and technological solutions to maintain the quality of cotton raw materials. These solutions include:

- **Optimization of the lubrication system:** We implemented the right lubrication system for the efficient operation of the separator vacuum valves. The right choice and amount of oil improved the system's performance, prevented friction and wear. Regular lubrication renewal, avoiding excess oil in the system, and extending the service life of components helped maintain cotton quality.
- **Use of variable materials:** Choosing high-quality materials and coatings for the separator vacuum valves helps reduce tribological phenomena. For example, wear-resistant materials or porous metal coatings increased the reliability of the system and helped prevent damage to the cotton fiber.
- **Correct system adjustment:** Optimal adjustment of the separator vacuum valve operation helped reduce friction and prevent wear. Regular inspection of the system played an important role in maintaining the quality of cotton raw materials.
- **Introduction of innovative technologies:** We have witnessed new methods to improve the efficiency

of separator vacuum valves using modern research in the field of tribology and innovative technologies. For example, by introducing tribological monitoring systems, we have detected friction and wear and taken prompt measures against them.

Discussion. Due to the significant impact of the operation of separator vacuum valves on the quality of cotton raw materials during cotton production, we had to conduct various theoretical analyses. The need to study many works aimed at maintaining the quality of cotton arises from the vacuum system. All this plays a major role in improving the quality of cotton, increasing its market value and improving production efficiency. Therefore, ensuring the effective operation of the separator vacuum valve is an important factor for obtaining high-quality products in the cotton industry.

Conclusion. Tribological phenomena in the operation of separator vacuum valves directly affect the quality of cotton raw materials. Friction, wear, and lubrication system malfunctions can damage the cleanliness, structure, and quality of cotton. To overcome these problems, innovative technologies, a proper lubrication system, high-quality materials, and regular system inspections are necessary. Controlling and optimizing tribological phenomena is essential for producing quality products in the cotton industry.

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